

ENHANCING STUDENTS' READING COMPREHENSION THROUGH GUIDED READING STRATEGIES

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Abstract. This action research utilized the observation design. The observation served as a guide to identify the problems and accordingly employ interventions such as guided reading activities. In gathering the data needed, the teacher-researcher used an observational approach and utilized a questionnaire responded by the identified students who struggling readers according to activities given by the researcher. The participants of this research are the 20 selected first-year college students of the College of Teacher Education during the second semester of School Year 2021-2022. With the appropriate reading comprehension tests administered to the subjects, these students were identified as those who needed intervention. It is hoped that the result of the study is disseminated to other English teachers who can effectively utilize the information gained and continue with research using other efficient methods in conducting similar action research and that teachers should purposefully evaluate students' reading comprehension skills to accordingly look into certain deficiencies and difficulties they encounter and employ the most appropriate and relevant interventions such as guided reading strategies to further enhance their reading comprehension skills.

Keywords. guided reading strategies, reading comprehension

1 Introduction

Reading is an activity performed to develop an understanding of a subject or topic. Reading is an essential skill that individuals need to process to be successful in life. Reading keeps individuals informed, up-to-date, and thinking. Reading is both a receptive and active process. It is a dynamic process in which the reader is searching for connections of ideas in the text. Reading requires the utilization of many mental processes as information is collected, processed, and analyzed. Also, reading is a source of enjoyment for individuals (Li and Wilhelm, 2020).

In addition, reading is one of the four skills that need to be learned besides listening, speaking, and writing. Reading has a considerable role in language teaching to strengthen the skills that are acquired by the students in listening, speaking, and writing (Maxom, 2021: 139).

Reading comprehension can be defined as the ability to understand a text, analyze the information, and interpret correctly what the writer is stating. "No one process defines reading comprehension by itself, but together they provide a fairly accurate account of the processes required for fluent reading." (Grabe and Stoller, 2020:17). Reading Comprehension can greatly affect the success of learning on the learner's part.

According to Babayiğit and Stainthorp, 2021, reading comprehension is a complex process that involves many variables. These variables include general language skills, background knowledge, comprehension strategies, knowledge of the text, and working memory. This leads Perfetti, et al. (2021) to state that the multifaceted nature of the processes involved in reading comprehension makes it very difficult for the construction of theoretical models of reading comprehension. It is challenging to capture all of the complex relationships involved in the process.

Another variable that has been identified as being related to reading comprehension is the size of the vocabulary of the reader. Hsueh-Chao and Nation (2020) estimated that readers must know about 98% of the words in a text to be able to understand the text without any other assistance. Additionally, the exposure to new words must be repeated for understanding to develop. Ten exposures or more are required for a new word to be acquired by the reader (Nation and Wang, 2019). "Vocabulary knowledge can influence reading comprehension in two ways: directly through its effect on the semantics of the text as well as indirectly through its effect on word reading skills," stated Babayiğit (2021). Grabe and Stoller (2022) indicated that reading ability is more than just phonemic awareness and phonic skills and that vocabulary size needs to be addressed by teachers.

As observed among the first-year college students of the College of Teacher Education, learners have manifested difficulties in comprehending what they read, which affects learning. Thus, this action research is conducted to help first-year college students enhance their reading comprehension skills. It is along this premise that the teacher-researcher is prompted to provide solutions by employing guided reading activities.

2 Action Research Question

The teacher-researcher sought to enhance the first-year college students' reading comprehension skills through guided reading activities.

The researcher aimed to answer the following specific questions.

1. What is the reading comprehension level of first-year college students?
2. How does the vocabulary of the students affect their reading comprehension?
3. What are the other factors that affect the reading comprehension of the students?

3 Proposed Innovation, Intervention, and Strategy

Guided reading strategies are often used to help students who struggle with reading comprehension. Pre-reading, during-reading, and post-reading strategies are combined to facilitate learning and enhance literacy. Through the implementation of guided reading strategies, students become aware of how print works (Kasten, Kristo, & McClure, 2020), and students struggling with reading comprehension are better able to create meaning.

"In guided reading, teachers show students the "tricks of the trade," then provide focused support to help them become independent readers and writers," (Kasten, Kristo, & McClure, 2015, p. 286). Teaching guided reading strategies to students provides them with the tools to enhance reading comprehension. By also focusing on Freebody & Luke's (2020) four reader roles, which exemplify pre-, during, and post-reading strategies, educators can help students with reading comprehension.

According to Shane Mac Donnchaidh, 2022, guided reading activities and strategies can be employed to enhance students' reading comprehension. These can be grouped into three useful categories: Prediction (What do you think will happen next?), Clarification and questioning- (Which parts of the book did you find difficult? What questions do you have about these?), and Summarizing (What is this book about? What happens?)

The first Strategy is Prediction, which encourages students to draw on their prior learning and experiences to allow them to make educated guesses on what may follow in the story. Prediction activities are great activities to hone your students' predictive abilities and comprehension skills, and they can be repeated often.

While prediction begins with the mostly pre-reading activities outlined above, there will be ample opportunities for the student reader to make further predictions throughout the reading of the book too.

Working on using prediction strategies in guided reading encourages the student to read closely for inferences and other clues that will indicate the journey the text may take. It also encourages the students to pay close attention to the content of the text as they read. This kind of holistic approach to reading improves overall comprehension of a text. In terms of guided reading, the second strategy which is, clarification and questioning refers to first identifying the difficult parts of the text, before making sense of them through a variety of clarification techniques.

These techniques can be as simple as looking up a word in a dictionary. There are other tools available to students, however. Often, when students look up the meaning of a word in a dictionary it helps clarify the meaning of that part of the text in the short term, but sometimes the word's definition is not retained for the next time the student comes across it. Sometimes the student should use other techniques to work out the meaning, such as employing contextual clues.

A teacher can employ Clarification and Question Prompts like drills employing sentence starters are a great way to effectively train our students to clarify and question and to help internalize these strategies. Begin with the clarification

prompts to help students identify the areas of the text they are unsure of, before moving to the question prompts to help them begin to work out the meaning and significance within the text. Examples of Clarification Prompts; “This part is difficult because...” “I didn’t understand when...” etc.

When the students have identified the vocabulary, phrases, sentences, paragraphs, and sections that are giving them trouble, they can then move on to forming questions using the following question prompts: the four Ws and 1 H questions (What, When, Where Why and How)

These prompts help students to identify more closely the source of their confusion when reading a text and to learn to ask for assistance. In the process of receiving an answer to their questions, they begin to broaden their understanding of a range of techniques they can later employ in independent reading to clarify the meaning of a text for themselves.

The last strategy is Summarizing which is an important skill for students to develop. It helps students to identify the most important parts of a text or story and to learn to ignore irrelevant details and information too. Students who practice summarizing learn to integrate the details and the main ideas of a text in a meaningful way. Summarization is useful for fiction and nonfiction genres alike.

A simple way to encourage students to summarize a story is to ask them to paraphrase it in their own words. As it will be highly unlikely, that they will have memorized the entire story word for word, paraphrasing the story will allow you to assess their overall understanding of what they have read.

Getting guided reading started in the classroom requires lots of planning and organization at the beginning of the year, but this initial investment of time and effort reaps rich rewards for students that are reflected in their rapid progress. Once clear procedures and routines are established, your students will become more adept at applying the broad range of strategies to a wide range of text types.

4 Action Research Methods

4.1 Participants and/or Other Sources of Data and Information

The participants of this research are the 20 selected first-year college students of the College of Teacher Education during the second semester of the School Year 2021-2022. With the appropriate reading comprehension tests administered to the subjects, these students were identified as those who needed intervention.

4.2 Data Gathering Methods

This action research utilized the observation design. The observation served as a guide to identify the problems and accordingly employ interventions such as guided reading activities.

In gathering data, the researcher used an observational approach and utilized a questionnaire responded by the identified students who struggling readers according to activities given by the researcher.

5 Action Research Work Plan and Timelines

Task	April 18-22	April 25-29	May 2-6	May 9-13	May 16-20	May 23-27
Submission of a work plan	X					
Preparation of Data Collection Instrument		X				
Data Collection Activities		X				
Data Analysis		X	X			
Initial Findings			X	X		
Final Report						
Policy Brief/ Policy Note and Publication and Dissemination					X	X

6 Action Research Work Plan and Timelines

Item	Cost	Number	Total
Workbooks	50	10	500
Newspapers and magazines	40	10	400
Travel brochures and manuals	donation	20	

7 Plans for Dissemination and Utilization

The researcher plans to disseminate the result of the study to other English teachers who can effectively utilize the information gained and continue with research using other efficient methods in conducting similar action research. Teachers should purposefully evaluate students' reading comprehension skills to look into certain deficiencies and difficulties they encounter. Teachers should employ the most appropriate and relevant interventions such as guided reading strategies to further enhance their reading comprehension skills.

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